

JIS

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JIS

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JIS

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

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Editorial 2018. November

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) wishes to announce the publication of *Volume 2, Issue 2, November 2018*. This issue contains research articles from interdisciplinary sciences such as psychology, education, sociology, gender studies, health sciences, and so forth. The JIS appreciates the authors' contributions to the journal's vision through constant interaction and the sharing of knowledge, in order to reach the wider readership community.

The academic journey towards the publishing of scientific and academic papers, and reaching the wider readership, has always been the exciting path that the JIS intended to follow. In its broader meaning, the journal's vision, to enrich beautiful minds towards intelligent minds, is an academic innovation to make academic research *Accessible, Available, Affordable, Acquirable, Achievable, and Admirable (A6)* to the wider readership community. Nevertheless, this vision is not easily achieved. Many daunting challenges need to be overcome. However, these challenges present an enthralling and adventurous academic journey for the JIS.

Our next issue will be published in May 2019. We invite authors, scientists, scholars, researchers, students, managers, and leaders from multi and interdisciplinary areas to submit their articles and essays on both conceptual and empirical studies.

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) also wishes to extend its appreciation and gratitude to the reviewers who contribute to the journal's vision through constructive comments and suggestions made to maintain the quality of this scientific and academic publication. The JIS contains a separate section called *Acknowledgment to Reviewers*, which contains the names of the reviewers who contributed their intellectual knowledge by timely reviewing the manuscripts.

Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS**

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
Founder and Editor-in-Chief
Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

JIS Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences, Volume 2, Issue 2, November. (2018)

Editorial 2018. November

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Note to Readers

Dear Readers,

I was recently attracted to the Volume 2, Issue 1 (May 2018) digital issue of Journal of Interdisciplinary Science (JIS) via a reference to one of my articles in the domain of Education. What I found at the website was a new journal, rudimentary but nevertheless quite impressive—the beginning of an inter-continently based academic journal accepting research and scholarly manuscripts from many disciplines for review and publication on a global basis.

I am a strong advocate of multidisciplinary thinking. During my academic career spanning approximately sixty years, I have been interested in a number of disciplines. First, as an undergraduate student at the University of Hawaii, I had an interest in Eastern Religions and Western Philosophies. As a graduate student at the University, I studied Economic Development (Developing Countries) and was fortunate to interact with students from all over Asia who were selected to attend the East-West Center. Subsequently, I attended Brown University in Providence, Rhode Island to earn a Ph.D. in mathematical economics. During my teaching tenure at the University of Rhode Island, I became interested in exploring some topics in Education.

Editor-in-Chief Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari and his editorial and support teams have done another note-worthy job of putting together Volume 2, Issue 2 of JIS in a timely fashion. The issue contains articles from such disciplines as Education, Gender Study, Political Science, Psychology, Sociology, etc. In my opinion, this journal is destined to gain a wide influence in the niche of non-specialized academic journals. I encourage you to give JIS first priority when it comes to consideration of where to submit your completed manuscript.

It is with great pleasure that I add my name to the list of Advisors to JIS and extend my gratitude to Editor-in-Chief — Dr. Rajbhandari and his staff for the completion of this issue.

Gilbert S. Suzawa, Ph.D.
Professor Emeritus of Economics
University of Rhode Island
U.S.A.

Table of content

Editorial <i>Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari</i> <i>Founder and Editor-in-Chief.</i>	iv
Note to Readers <i>Gilbert S. Suzawa</i> <i>University of Rhode Island</i>	v
The Contested and Expanding Meaning of Democracy <i>Asafa Jalata</i>	1
The Concept of Gender Crossing in the Deirdre McCloskey's Theory <i>Khitruk Ekaterina</i>	30
Effectiveness and Outcome Moderators of Computer-Based Health Education for an Adult Population: A systematic Review of Meta-Analytic Studies <i>Leontien E. Vreeburg, René F.W. Diekstra and Clemens M.H. Hosman</i>	38
The Influence of Time Perspective on Retention in United States Army Personnel <i>John W. Gaddy, Stephen P. Gonzalez, Jim Mirabella, Calvin A. Lathan, and Heather I. Scott</i>	70
Differences in Black Student Enrollment in Texas Doctoral Programs Over Time <i>Tama S. Hamrick and John R. Slate</i>	84
Teachers' Self-Efficacy in Handling Pupils with Emotional Problems: Basis for Teachers' Training Program <i>Ma. Gloria E. Liquido and Fritzie B. Mendez</i>	97
Problems and challenges of the gifted adolescent: School-related problems of the gifted adolescent <i>Hanna David</i>	113
Acknowledgement to reviewers <i>From the Desk of Editor-in-Chief</i>	132